

This electronic companion is part of the manuscript entitled Coordinating Strategic Aggregators in an Active Distribution Network for Providing Operational Flexibility which has been exclusively submitted to the 21st Power Systems Computation Conference (PSCC 2020). It comprises the proof of Nash equilibrium (NE) existence and uniqueness of the proposed induced non-cooperative game among strategic aggregators (Appendix A). We show this way that the proposed mechanism is efficient; the aggregators offer the optimal one at the maximum welfare for all of them and it is implemented in the NE of the induced non-cooperative game among strategic aggregators (Appendix B). We also prove the mechanism revenue adequacy, which implies that the coordinator never incurs a budget deficit (Appendix C). Moreover, in Appendix D we provide some technical parameters and data used in the case study.

APPENDIX A- THE PROOF OF NE UNIQUENESS

The proof can be divided into the following three steps:

- (i) The optimization problem of each aggregator is convex and Slater constraint qualification is satisfied. The feasible range is also convex and compact, i.e., closed and bounded. Therefore, the Karush-Kuhn-Tucker (KKT) conditions are necessary and sufficient for optimality.
- (ii) The non-cooperative game among aggregators is equivalent to variational inequality (VI) problem $VI(\mathbb{S}^{\text{AGG}}, U)$ with $U(\vec{s}) = (\nabla_{\vec{s}_i} u_i(\vec{s}_i, \vec{s}_{-i}))_{i \in \mathbb{I}}$ and $\mathbb{S}^{\text{AGG}} = \prod_{i \in \mathbb{I}} \mathbb{S}_i^{\text{AGG}}$. Here, set $\mathbb{S}_i^{\text{AGG}}$ is derived from constraint (1). The equivalence of the non-cooperative game and the VI problem is proven as given in [21, equation (18)]. The VI problem is defined as finding vector $\vec{s}^* \in \mathbb{S}^{\text{AGG}}$ such that:

$$(\vec{s} - \vec{s}^*)^T U(\vec{s}^*) \geq 0, \quad \forall \vec{s} \in \mathbb{S}^{\text{AGG}}. \quad (15)$$

- (iii) Set \mathbb{S}^{AGG} is convex. Function $U(\vec{s})$ is strongly monotone with respect to the elements of \vec{s} . Thus, problem $VI(\mathbb{S}^{\text{AGG}}, U)$ has a unique solution [21, equation (13)]. \square

APPENDIX B- THE PROOF OF NE IMPLEMENTATION

Let derive the equivalent VI problem of optimization problem (8a)-(8c). Note that the objective (8a) is strongly convex and constraints (8b)-(8c) lead us to a convex and compact set. Thus, the VI problem can be obtained [21, equation (18)]. By comparing this VI problem and the one obtained from the non-cooperative game among aggregators, it is observed that they are equivalent. As both of them have unique solution, then the NE of the non-cooperative game induced by the proposed mechanism is the optimal solution of problem (8a)-(8c). \square

APPENDIX C- THE PROOF OF BUDGET-BALANCED PROPERTY

If $\gamma \rightarrow \infty$, $v \rightarrow \infty$, and $\gamma/v \rightarrow \infty$, then the second term in (10) would be equal to zero in the NE; otherwise, the aggregators have incentive to deviate. It is observed that the sum of the first term over all $i \in \mathbb{I}$ is equal to $\pi \sum_{i \in \mathbb{I}} d_i(\vec{s}_i)$. Thus, the budget-balance property in NE is proved. \square

APPENDIX D- SENSITIVITY FACTORS

Sensitivity factors $R_{n,n'}^1$, $R_{n,n'}^2$, $R_{b,n'}^3$, $R_{b,n'}^4$, $R_{n,n'}^5$, and $R_{n,n'}^6$ are computed using existing methods, e.g., [19], [20] and illustrated in Figs. 7-12.

Fig. 7. Sensitivity factor $R_{n,n'}^1$.

Fig. 8. Sensitivity factor $R_{n,n'}^2$.

Fig. 9. Sensitivity factor $R_{b,n}^3$.

Fig. 10. Sensitivity factor $R_{b,n}^4$.

Fig. 11. Sensitivity factor $R_{1,n}^5$.

Fig. 12. Sensitivity factor $R_{1,n}^6$.